

Notes

Spectrophotometric Studies on Fe (ii)-2 Hydroxy-5 Methyl Acetophenone-Ethylenediamineanil Complex. Part I

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Manuscript received 15 March 1974; revised 10 February 1975;
accepted 31 March 1975.

THE 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone-ethylenediamine-anil has been reported to be a chelating agent for few metal ions¹. However, the spectrophotometric studies of its metal chelates have not been done systematically so far. The present work deals with the determination of composition and stability constant of Fe(ii) chelate with HMAEA reagent by Job's method of continuous variation^{2,3}, mole ratio method⁴ and slope ratio method⁵.

Experimental

Preparation of 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone-ethylene-diamine-anil¹.

2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone was prepared by Fries reaction of p-cresyl-acetate⁶. 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone (2.0 mole) and ethylene diamine (1.0 mole) in absolute alcohol were refluxed for one hour, when a yellow anil was obtained. It was recrystallised from alcohol m.p. 201°.

Reaction with Fe²⁺ ions: A stock solution of ferrous sulphate ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) was prepared in double distilled water and standardised by the general method. One percent ethanolic solution of the reagent was used. It gave reddish brown chelate with Fe²⁺ at pH 2.5-3.0.

Effect of pH: Preliminary experiments showed that the colour of the complex between pH 2.5 to 4.0 is reddish brown. At pH lower than 2.5, there is no coloration and above the pH 4, the complex was unstable. The study was therefore confined to the pH range 2.5 to 3.0 where maximum colour intensity was obtained. This pH range was obtained using sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer and the pH was measured by using the pH meter (Systronic) with glass electrode (0-13 pH) and a saturated calomel electrode.

Effect of Varying Solvent Composition: The complex remains soluble in ethanol water mixture (70:30) and the solution becomes turbid on further dilution with water. No change in colour has been observed on changing the composition of the solvent and the ethanolic solution of the complex remains stable for 24 hr.

Spectrophotometric Study:

Absorption Measurements: The absorbance measurements were carried out at 500 nm using "Spectronic 20".

An equimolar solutions of ferrous sulphate ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) and reagent solution in ethanol ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) in the ratio of 2:1, 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 at pH 2.5-3.0 were mixed and the final volume was made 10 ml by adding required amount of water and alcohol to keep alcohol water composition same in all cases. The absorption spectra of all solutions were recorded. In all cases the maximum absorption was found to be at 500 nm and 438 nm suggest that reagent forms only one type of complex with Fe²⁺ ion. The Beer's Law has been varified at 500 nm and 438 nm at pH 2.5-3.0.

Composition and Stability Constant of the Complex: Using Job's method^{2,3} molar ratio method⁴ and slope ratio method⁵, the stoichiometry of the Fe-HMAEA complex has been found to be 1:1. The stability constant calculated from these methods was 1.34×10^6 . The molar absorptivity of the complex is found to be $1:1 \times 10^3$.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks to Dr. K.A. Thaker for providing the research facility and giving encouragement.

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New Synthesis of 6-Nitro-4-Hydroxy and 8-Nitro-4-Hydroxy Cinnolines

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Manuscript received 12 February 1975; accepted 17 March 1975

CINNOLINE, a heterocyclic binuclear base containing two vicinal nitrogen atoms was first synthesized by Richter¹ by cyclisation of an aryldiazonium compound containing an unsaturated group at the ortho-position. 4-Hydroxy cinnolines were synthesized from 2-nitrophenylpropionic acid as well as 2-amino-phenylpropionic acid² and 2-aminophenylacetylenes³. Further, cinnolines not containing any hydroxy group at the 4-position was synthesized by a number of workers, by cyclising the diazotised o-aminophenyl-

ethylenes⁴⁻¹⁸. Syntheses of 4-hydroxy cinnolines from diazotised o-aminoacetophenones has also been thoroughly reported¹⁴⁻¹⁸.

A large number of derivatives of cinnolines and 4-hydroxy cinnolines have been reported with their biological and pharmacological activity. Nitrocinnolines have been prepared by nitrating cinnolines and the 4-hydroxy derivatives of 6- and 8-nitro 4-hydroxy cinnolines have also been synthesized by diazotising acid cyclising the 5- and 3-nitro 2-aminoacetophenones¹⁹. In the present work 6- and 8-nitro 4-hydroxy cinnolines were prepared by coupling the diazonium salt of 4- and 2-nitraniline with malonic ester²⁰. These azo-compounds (I) on hydrolysis and decarboxylation gave the corresponding 4- and 2-nitrophenylazo acetic acids (II) which on cyclisation with PPA afforded 6- and 8-nitro cinnolines (III) (Scheme-A).

Experimental

4-Nitrophenylazo acetic acid (II): To an ice cold solution of malonic ester (0.1 mole) in acetone containing sodium acetate was gradually added a diazotised solution of 4-nitraniline (0.1 mole) with stirring and cooling. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 1 hr at 0° - 5°, after which was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The orange coloured azo compound (I) separated was filtered washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol.

The compound (I) obtained as above was hydrolysed by boiling with excess of alkali (3-4 hr.). This mixture was then cooled and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and boiled for 1-1½ hrs to bring about the decarboxylation. The precipitated compound (II) was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from 50% alcohol. M. P. 205°, yield 69%. (Found: C, 45.69; H, 3.24; N, 19.87; C₈H₇N₃O₄ requires C, 45.94; H, 3.35; N, 20.09%).

2-Nitrophenylazoacetic acid (II): A procedure to obtain compound (II) similar as above was adopted. It was recrystallised from 50% alcohol. M. P. 171°-72°. Yield 56%. (Found: C, 45.76; H, 3.39; N, 19.92, C₈H₇N₃O₄ requires: C, 45.94; H, 3.35; N, 20.09%).

6-Nitro-4-hydroxy cinnoline (III): The pure compound II (4-nitrophenylazoacetic acid) was mixed with PPA (30 g P₂O₅: 18 ml H₃PO₄) at 60°-65°. The mixture was then heated to 100°-105° for 1 hr with stirring giving effervescence. After which the temperature was raised to 130°-35° for ½ hr. with stirring. The mass was cooled and carefully neutralised with ammonium hydroxide to pH 6-7. The precipitated compound was filtered washed with water and repeatedly crystallised from acetic acid, to give a red brown crystalline compound m. p. 329-30°. The mixture M. P. of this compound with the compound prepared from 5-Nitro-

2-amino-acetophenone by the method of Borsche and Herbert¹⁴ showed no depression. Yield 56% (Found: C, 49.20; H, 2.93; N, 21.23, C₈H₅N₃O₃ requires, C, 50.3; H, 2.60; N, 22.00%).

8-Nitro-4-hydroxy cinnoline (III): 2-Nitrophenylazoacetic acid (II) was subjected to the above procedure. A reddish brown mass obtained gave light brown needles after several crystallisations from alcohol. M. P. 274°-75°. Yield 47%. The mixture m. p. of this compound with the one prepared from 3-Nitro-2-aminoacetophenone by the method of Borsche and Herbert¹⁴ showed no depression, (Found: C, 49.70; H, 2.90; N, 21.08%).

U. V. spectral data of 6- and 8-nitro-4-hydroxy cinnolines closely resembled the one reported by Hearn et al²¹.

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Aldehydes as Corrosion Inhibitors for 70/30 Brass in Potassium Persulphate Solutions

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Manuscript received 21 February 1972 ; revised 11 February 1975 ; accepted 31 March 1975

POTASSIUM persulphate solutions can be used to remove oxide layers from metal surface, hence inhibitors are necessary.

From earlier work in this laboratory it was found the furfuraldehyde^{1,2}, salicylaldehyde^{1,2} and paraldehyde² are satisfactory inhibitors for the corrosion of copper(1) and 63/37 brass² in potassium persulfate solutions. The present article reports furfuraldehyde, salicylaldehyde and paraldehyde as corrosion inhibitors for 70/30 brass in 0.2M potassium persulfate solutions.

70/30 brass supplied by M/s. Kamani Metals was used for the study. The preparation of specimens and corrosion tests were carried out as per our earlier publication³.

The effect of time on performance of inhibitors is given in Table 1. The ratios of copper and zinc going in solution are given in Table 2. The influence of current density on the cathode and anode potentials of 70/30 brass in 0.2M K₂S₂O₈ in the presence and absence of inhibitors is given in fig. 1. (Table 1, Fig. 1)

Influence of current density on the cathode and anode potentials of 70/30 brass in 0.2M potassium persulphate in the presence and absence of inhibitors

- 0.2M K₂S₂O₈
- ×—× 26.1 ml/l paraldehyde
- 8.7 ml/l Salicylaldehyde
- △—△ 2.17 ml/l Salicylaldehyde
- 34.8 ml/l Furfuraldehyde

TABLE 1

Inhibitor concentration ml/l.	70/30 Brass — Potassium Persulphate				
	Corrosion loss of Specimen (mg./dm ²) and % inhibition for an immersion period of : (Values in the bracket represent percentage inhibition)				
	5 min.	15 min.	30 min.	60 min.	90 min.
Paraldehyde					
0.00 ml/l	202.5	564.3	1152.0	2176.0	3042.0
17.40 ml/l	(—)	(—)	(—)	(—)	(—)
26.10 ml/l	3.6	9.7	7.5	33.8	53.2
	(98.2)	(98.3)	(99.4)	(98.4)	(98.3)
Furfuraldehyde					
26.10 ml/l	—	—	6.1	15.2	30.3
	(—)	(—)	(99.5)	(99.3)	(99.0)
Salicylaldehyde					
4.35 ml/l	1.1	1.9	21.3	113.1	504.2
	(99.4)	(99.6)	(98.2)	(94.8)	(81.5)
8.70 ml/l	0.3	0.3	1.4	6.1	8.3
	(99.8)	(99.8)	(99.9)	(99.8)	(99.7)
	5.3	9.1	16.1	40.1	60.4
	(97.3)	(98.4)	(98.6)	(98.1)	(97.1)

Observations : The rate of corrosion of 70/30 brass in 0.2M potassium persulphate increases with time.

Paraldehyde : At 17.40 ml/l concentration, paraldehyde effectively retards the corrosion of 70/30 brass in 0.2M potassium persulphate for all the duration studied. At lower inhibitor concentrations, the effect of paraldehyde is immediate, but the efficiency decreases with the passage of time.